

BASIC APPROACHES TO GENDER EDUCATION OF STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408531>

Abstract: In this thesis, opinions are expressed about the theoretical foundations of the main approaches to gender education of students and youth. Also, a discussion about the basics of organizing the system of education and training activities based on the gender approach in the educational process is described.

Key words: sociologist, physiological, psychological, gender approach, cortex, concept.

Introduction.

Today, the process of active modernization of the capitalist world continues along with informatization, technologization, strengthening of nationalistic tendencies, violation of material and spiritual balance. "The world has reached the limit of market-capitalist development," says A. I. Subbeto¹. The ongoing global civilizational changes throughout the world are contributing to the birth of new forms of organizing people's lives, changing the traditional world as a whole, disrupting its stability and stability. Since education is the main superstructure of society, it is responsible for the formation of a person, his spiritual image, moral development. Education, integrated with education from a socio-cultural point of view, is "a blessing of social importance... a purposeful process of education and learning for the benefit of the individual, family, society, and the state..."² considering that it is considered as Objective reality forces us to solve the issue of education, to remember what happened, what it is, what place social education will occupy in the context of control of the future society.

Without studying the terminological analysis of the concept of "social education", let's consider its meaning. M.A. Galaguzova determines that the uniqueness of social education is determined by the adjective "social"³. This means that social learning can be viewed from different perspectives. From the point of view of Academician A.V. Mudrik, social education includes the influence

¹ Суббетто, А. И. Социогенетика: системогенетика, общественный интеллект, образовательная генетика и мировое развитие. — М.: Логос. — 168 с.

² Закон РФ Об образовании // Официальные документы. Российская газета 21.12.2012. Ст. 52, с. 8. Ст. 2, с. 1.

³ Галагузова, М. А. Социальная педагогика: Курс лекций / Под общей ред. М.А. Галагузовой. - М.: Гуманит. Изд. Центр ВПАДОС, 2000. - 416с.

of society on a specific person or group of people. In this case, the society acts as a customer of social education implemented through various organizations and institutions. According to L.V. Mardakhayev, social education reflects a meaningful direction, its vector is aimed at preparing a person for the life of society⁴. At the same time, institutions of socialization (*family, educational institutions, religious denominations, etc.*), their values, meanings, and relationships are directly involved in the process of social education. According to our research, L.V. Mardakhayev's statement is important. "Education is education aimed at creating conditions for the self-determination and socialization of the student, based on the socio-cultural, spiritual and moral values, rules and norms of behavior accepted in the society. is an activity organized in the system. individual, family, society, state".

Education in any society has certain goals determined by a certain historical period, national culture and state requirements (dominant ideology). Therefore, the question of forming a person who is able to live here and now, who is able to preserve and increase the wealth of society, and to contribute to its harmonious development, always arises. Accordingly, we not only help the individual (child, teenager, youth, adult and elderly) to enter the ever-changing society, teach him to feel "comfortable", but also constantly It is about forming a desire for self-development and self-improvement. Undoubtedly, it is necessary to develop socially important qualities that help a person change the world, make him kinder and more beautiful, nobler and wiser, moderately "feminine" and moderately "manly".

From this point of view, it is addressed to gender issues, education of young people based on gender approach, taking into account the interests of social-gender groups of the society and the demands of the new century.

For the effectiveness of the development of the social education system in higher education institutions of pedagogy, it is necessary to distinguish the theoretical and methodological approaches that are the foundation and basis of scientific research. For the completeness and reliability of the problem disclosure, it is fair to work with not one, but several approaches whose instructions complement each other.

Let's consider and analyze the concept of "approach". According to the Philosophical Dictionary, "approach" is "a set of syntagmatic and pragmatic structures and mechanisms in knowledge and/or practice that characterize

⁴ Мардахаев, Л. В. Педагогика среды: учебное пособие. — Новосибирск: Изд-во НГПУ, 2009.

competing strategies and programs in philosophy, science, politics, or other fields. Apparently, this phenomenon reflects ongoing changes in the life structure of a person and society in different periods of development, notes qualitative changes in the forms of life activities. The analysis of the source base confirms the opinion that most authors are in a defined context. The problem approach reflects a formalized conceptualization of pedagogical reality and adheres to the position that it is determined by "ideas, principles and concepts. It defines, on the one hand, already established ideas that are being implemented in practice, and on the other hand, new, weakly expressed theoretical plans. E.N. Stepanov and L.M. Luzina correctly define as stated: "This is the direction of the teacher or the head of the educational institution in the implementation of his actions, encouraging the use of a certain set of concepts, ideas and methods of pedagogical activity."⁵ Arguing about this interpretation, we are not only about the application of forms, methods, methods, tools at the local level in the educational environment, but also about their implementation in order to effectively manage the pedagogical process, the success of which depends on the new trajectory of the educational movement - it depends on the individual a process that allows not only to adapt to the dynamically developing social space, but also to change it.

V. I. Zagvyazinsky offers a slightly different interpretation from the position of the management aspect, which is as follows: "*Management approaches are methods of analyzing the object of social management, assessing its state and the possibilities of change using management tools.*" In this case, the "approach" is considered as a lever of production management, the main concepts of which are market, product, consumers, suppliers and producers.

Let's consider and analyze the approaches that are the basis of scientific research, that form the epistemological integrity of our problem, that force us to look differently at the processes of personality formation. Currently, the following approaches are clearly formed in local pedagogy and in the context of studying our problem: competence-based, axiological, philosophical-anthropological, systematic, cultural, synergetic. Let's dwell on the characteristics of each of them.

Thus, according to L.M. Mitina, "pedagogical competence" includes not only the knowledge component, but also the ways and means of implementing things accumulated in activities, communication and personal development (*self-*

⁵ Степанов, Е. Н., Лузина, Л. М. Педагогу о современных подходах и концепциях воспитания. — М., 2002. — С.

development)⁶. In this interpretation, the author examines competence through the prism of professionalism and distinguishes two interacting substructures: activity and communication.

References:

1. Sharifzoda, S. (2023). System of preparing future teachers for professional activity on the socialization of students on the base of gender approach. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(11), 378-387.
2. Sharifzoda, S. (2023). Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni gender yondashuv asosida ijtimoiylashtirishga yo'naltirilgan kasbiy-pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlashga oid nazariy yondashuvlar. *Молодые ученые*, 1(18), 10-15.
3. Sharifzoda Sardorbek O'Razboy Tabib Ugli. (2023). Theoretical principles of preparing future teachers for the professional-pedagogical activity directed to the socialization of students on the base of a gender approach *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(11), 162-166.
4. Sharifzoda, S. (2023). Pedagogical and psychological directions of preparing professional activities for the socialization of future teachers on the basis of a gender approach. *Development and innovations in science*, 2(11), 22-28.
5. Sharifzoda, M. (2023). Gender xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda chet tillarini o'rgatishdagi asosiy omillar. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(11), 84-87.
6. Khudoyberganov, D., & Safaeva, D. (2023). Gender yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarni ijtimoiylashtirishga yo'naltirish mexanizmlari. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 3(5 Part 2), 42-46.
7. Sharifzoda, S. (2023). Oliy pedagogik ta'limda gender yondashuvini amalga oshirishning ijtimoiy zarurati. *Science and innovation*, 2(Special Issue 9), 263-268.
8. ўғли Шарифзода, С. Ў. Т. Ўқувчиларда таянч компетенцияларни шакллантириш асосида ижтимоий компетентлиликни таркиб топтириш мазмуни.
9. qizi Safayeva, D. H. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim o'quvchilarida tayanch kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishda integrativ yondashuvdan foydalanishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari.
10. SHARIFZODA, S. O'quvchilarda tayanch kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishda integrativ yondashuvdan foydalanishning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari. *Pedagogik ahorat*, 78.

⁶ Митина, Л. М. Психология профессионального развития. —М., 1998. —С. 46.

11. Ugli, S. S. U. T. (2020). The Use Of An Integrative Approach In The Formation Of Basic Competencies In Students As A Socio-Didactic Necessity. JCR, 7(12), 3115-3120.
12. Sharifzoda, S. U. (2021). Pedagogical aspects of the process of formation of basic competencies using integrated learning materials. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 06 (98), 760-763.
13. SHARIFZODA, S. (2023). Strategies for preparing future teachers for pedagogical activity on the basis of a gender approach. International bulletin of engineering and technology, 3(4), 173-176.
14. Sharifzoda, M. (2022). Using The Didactic Views Of Abu Ali Ibn Sino In The Formation Of Basic Competences In Students. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 1(7), 130-136.
15. Угли, Ш. С. У. Т. (2020). Интегративный подход в формировании базовых компетенций учащихся в образовательном процессе. International scientific review, (LXXIII), 77-79.
16. UZBEKISTAN, U. (2019). Possibilities Of Using An Integrative Approach In The Formation Of Key Competences Of Pupils. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 7(10).
17. Sardorbek, O., Sharifzoda, L., Xudoyberganov, D. Y. O. G. L., & Safayeva, D. H. Q. (2022). Umumiy O'rta Ta'lim O'quvchilarida Tayanch Kompetensiyalarni Shakllantirishda Integrativ Yondashuvdan Foydalanishning Pedagogik Shartsharoitlari. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(7), 134-139.
18. Sharifzoda, S. O., Xudoyberganov, D. Y. O. G. L., & Safayeva, D. H. Q. (2022). Umumiy O'rta Ta'lim O'quvchilarida Tayanch Kompetensiyalarni Shakllantirishda Integrativ Yondashuvdan Foydalanishning Pedagogik Shartsharoitlari. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(6), 199-205.
19. Sardorbek, O., Sharifzoda, L., & Karimov, H. Q. (2022). gender yondashuv asosida o'quvchi-qizlarda ijtimoiymadaniy kompetentlikni rivojlantirish omillari. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(7), 371-375.
20. "Integrative methods of formation of basic competencies in students" S Sharifzoda - Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation., 3., 32.
21. "Possibilities of using an integrative approach in the formation of key competences of pupils" S.O. Sharifzoda - European Journal of Research and Reflection in ...,44-47., 2019.

22. “Ўқувчиларда таянч компетенцияларни шакллантиришда интегратив ёндашувнинг аҳамиятли жиҳатлари” SO Sharifzoda - Таълим ва инновацион тадқиқотлар-7.2021 йил. Б, 2019
23. “Таянч kompetentsiyalarni shakllantirish asosida o’quvchilarda ijtimoiy kompetentlilikni tarkib toptirish mazmuni” SO Sharifzoda - Pedagogika va psixologiya.№-1, 2022
24. “Интегративный подход в формировании базовых компетенций Учащих в образовательном процессе. International scientific review of the problems and prospects of modern science and education: LXXIII international correspondence scientific and practical conference” S.O. Sharifzoda - Boston. USA, 2020
25. Sharifzoda, S. O. Strategies for forming competencies in students based on an integrative approach. European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies/ISSN, 2750-8587.

